

pH Dependence of Solubility of Calcium-Zinc Hydroxylapatites

S. V. CHIRANJEEVI RAO

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur

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The solubilities of solid solutions of Calcium-zinc hydroxylapatites determined in the pH range 5.0 to 8.0 decreases with increase in pH of the dissolving medium. This is due to the dissolved phosphate ions function as proton acceptors and being salts of weak acid undergoes hydrolysis in aqueous media and at a given pH it was found to decrease steadily till about 60 mole % of zinc hydroxylapatite composition was reached and thereafter an increase in solubility with greater proportions of ZnHA in the solid solutions—a well known phenomenon observed due to destabilisation of the crystal lattice observed in case of allotropes.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, is the major inorganic constituent of human skeletal system¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Zn}^{2+}$ exchange in CaHA is of biological importance as it explains the incorporation of zinc into the human skeletal system. This exchange process results in the formation of solid solutions of calcium-zinc hydroxylapatites due to the closeness of ionic radii of Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å) and Zn^{2+} (0.77 Å)³ according to the following equation

While the pH dependence of solubility of CaHA has been thoroughly investigated⁴, similar studies on ZnHA and its solid solutions with CaHA are not available. The present work reports a study of (i) the pH dependence of solubility of calcium and zinc hydroxylapatite in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, (ii) the solubility effect with increase of zinc content in the solid solutions at fixed pH value.

The details of preparation and identification of CaHA , ZnHA and Ca-ZnHA in the form of solid solutions were reported earlier⁵. The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro analytical determination of phosphate in the saturated solutions of the sample. Potassium acid phthalate—sodium hydroxide and sodium diethyl barbiturate—Hydrochloric acid were used as buffer combinations of the medium of equilibration. The pH was measured with a line operated Beckmann pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2 g of 200 mesh (B.S.S.) solute was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbon dioxide free doubly distilled water taken in an air tight polythene container and was shaken mechanically at a regulated speed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to stimulate biological conditions. At the end of the desired period of equilibration required for the attainment of saturation which was determined previously through dissolution kinetics,

the systems were separately filtered through IG_4 crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁶.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the sample were given in Table I and a graphical representation of the solubility behaviour was shown in Fig. 1A. The experimental Wt% errors of the determinations of Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} when present together as in the solid solutions were respectively less 0.20, 0.25 and 0.00 while the corresponding errors when PO_4^{3-} was present either with Ca^{2+} or Zn^{2+} as in the case of CaHA or ZnHA was 0.00. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total of 10 g atoms of calcium, and/or Zn^{2+} , the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated and given in Table I. The

g. atom ratios of $\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Zn}}{\text{P}}$ in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of the chemical analysis and was found to be 1.68 (theoretical 1.67). The dissolution of CaHA can be considered to be initiated by the hydrolysis of PO_4^{3-} of the hydroxylapatite lattice which leads to the formation of $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ according to the following equations.

Exactly analogous equations can be proposed for the zinc species. So CaHA and ZnHA basically undergo the same mode of dissolution leading to the formation of corresponding tribasic phosphate and hydroxide, the solubility being governed by the solubility product of latter and thus at a given pH CaHA is more soluble than ZnHA (see Fig. 1B); the decrease of solubility of the samples with increase in pH can be explained on the basis of the common ion effect applied to the solubility products⁷. The

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM AND ZINC HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sl. No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	Molecular volume	g-atomic ratio Ca+Zn/P
	Ca	Pb	P			
1	39.80	—	18.52	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.3	1.68
2	30.80	11.81	17.67	$\text{Ca}_{8.1}\text{Zn}_{1.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	335.1	1.65
3	21.72	23.53	16.83	$\text{Ca}_{6.0}\text{Zn}_{4.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	335.0	1.67
4	14.23	33.52	16.15	$\text{Ca}_{4.1}\text{Zn}_{5.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	329.0	1.68
5	7.32	42.43	15.47	$\text{Ca}_{2.2}\text{Zn}_{7.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	328.4	1.68
6	—	52.10	14.77	$\text{Zn}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	326.7	1.68

Fig. 1A.

Fig. 1B.

samples being salts of weak acid undergo hydrolysis in aqueous media and the dissolved phosphate can function as a proton acceptor⁸. The solubility at a given pH, the samples should normally decrease as percentage of ZnHA increases as found upto 60 mole % of ZnHA in solid solutions. The solubility is expected to increase thereafter if sufficient increase in ZnHA so appreciably destabilise the crystal lattice—a well known phenomena observed in case of allotropes, less stable allotropes are more soluble for instance of aragonite (orthorhombic) is less stable and hence has greater solubility than calcite having a more symmetrical thombohedral crystal lattice. Thus the increase in trend of solubility of solid solutions with higher proportions of ZnHA could be explained.

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